

Use of Phenolic Acids in the Detection, Separation and Estimation of Metals. Part III. Gravimetric Estimation of Uranium.

BY PABITRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

In the existing methods of gravimetric estimation of uranium, the latter is precipitated, converted into U_3O_8 or UO_2 and weighed as such. The forms in which uranium is precipitated from its solution (for gravimetric estimation) are $(NH_4)_2U_2O_7$, UF_4 and UO_2S ; all of them on ignition in air are changed into U_3O_8 .

It has been observed that from a neutral or faintly acid solution or from a solution containing suspended $(NH_4)_2U_2O_7$ uranium can be quantitatively precipitated by tannic acid followed by the addition of a solution of sodium acetate and some ammonium salts (preferably chloride or nitrate) or of a slightly ammoniacal ammonium acetate solution. This uranium precipitate on ignition in air is changed into U_3O_8 . The above observations serve as a gravimetric method for the estimation of uranium, which is dealt with in the present paper.

For the quantitative precipitation of uranium from its solution, the following points are to be observed.

1. When uranium is present as nitrate, chloride or sulphate in neutral or faintly acid solution, addition of some alkali or ammonium acetate is essential. The acetate added should not be less than the amount required to neutralise the mineral acidity which will be liberated in the reaction.

2. Addition of alkali acetate must be followed by an ammonium salt for coagulating the uranium precipitate; its amount depends on the strength of the uranium solution, with very weak solution greater amount of the salt requires to be added. In the case of the acetate solution, containing no free mineral acids, addition of an acetate is not required.

3. In the presence of free mineral acids or an excess of acetic acid, the acidity is to be neutralised by adding ammonium hydroxide till the solution is just opalescent.

4. If ammonium acetate is used instead of sodium acetate, it should be made faintly ammoniacal.

The precipitate obtained from uranyl nitrate solution by tannic acid and other reagents stated above is found to be free from nitrate and acetate radicles. The uranium precipitate with excess of water forms pseudo-solution, chocolate-brown in colour like that of the precipitate; addition of ammonium salts to this solution gives rise to the original precipitate. The uranium precipitate is found to be very stable. It does not break even on boiling with ammonium or sodium hydroxides, nor does it dissolve in ammonium or sodium carbonate. It is readily soluble in dilute mineral acids and in excess of dilute acetic acid giving colourless solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

An aqueous solution of uranyl nitrate is prepared. With this solution, several estimations of uranium are carried out according to the standard method. Uranium is first precipitated as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{U}_2\text{O}_7$ by ammonium chloride and freshly prepared ammonia and then ignited to U_3O_8 and weighed. Also side by side from this solution uranium is estimated according to the present method. The results of the above estimations are tabulated below :

Weight of U_3O_8 .			
Uranium solution taken (c.c.)	Ammonium hydroxide method.	Tannic acid method.	Remarks.
10	0.1434 g.	0.1436 g.	
5	0.0718	0.0722	
..	0.0710	0.0721	With original
..	0.0720	0.0719	uranium
3	Estimation not possible.	0.0430	solution.
..	..	0.0434	
2	..	0.0285	
..	..	0.0239	
1	..	0.0144	
..	..	0.0148	
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20		0.0286 g.	
15		0.0217	The uranium
..		0.0219	solution is diluted
10		0.0144	10 times.
..		0.0144	
5		0.0072	
..		0.0073	
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10	0.1405 g.	0.1402 g.	With fresh
..	0.1400	—	uranium
5	—	0.0700	solution.

To estimate uranium according to the tannic acid method, the best condition for its precipitation is to add 2 c.c. of 2% tannic acid for each 0.012 g. of uranium. After the addition of tannic acid, which produces a deep brown coloration, the solution is just boiled and to this ammoniacal 10% ammonium acetate solution is added with stirring till the upper liquid becomes clear. For a certain amount of uranium, the quantity of ammonium acetate varies with concentration, *e.g.*, for 0.012 g. uranium in 1 c.c., 0.5 c.c. of ammonium acetate is sufficient for the complete precipitation and for the same amount in a volume of 10 c.c. at least 1.5 c.c. ammonium acetate are required. The precipitate of uranium obtained in this way is chocolate-brown in colour and is very voluminous; it affords moderately quick filtration. When a solution contains purely uranium salt, the precipitate is filtered and the last traces of the precipitate are taken on the filter by warm and slightly ammoniacal 2% ammonium nitrate solution. The precipitate is then ready for wet incineration. When the precipitate requires decantation washing (say, in the presence of sodium or other salts not precipitable by tannic acid and ammonium acetate), it is done by stirring the precipitate with 100-120 c.c. of warm ammoniacal 2% ammonium nitrate solution and each time allowed to settle for 10 minutes and then the clear liquid is decanted through the filter.

The advantages of the present method are:—

(1) Accurate results are obtained. (2) With small amount of uranium, the gravimetric estimation is fairly good. (3) There is no possibility of low results, which may occur in the standard method, due to the presence of slight ammonium carbonate in ammonia.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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